

TRANSFER OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS DURING TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

This article provides comprehensive information on the transfer of phraseological units. Pupils are given on equivalent translation of artistic works in the process of translation.

One of the most difficult and controversial tasks in the translation process is the translation of phraseological units. Therefore, the process is the translation of phraseological units requires a lot of responsibility, creativity, care and skill from the person who translates. In terms of comparison, the study of Phraseologisms is of great importance, since they serve to enrich the speech activity of students. When teaching the Russian language, creating an adequate translation, understanding the author's style of translation, the ability to reflect the national flavor in translation is an important link. The translation of phraseological units is of great importance in reflecting the individual author's style in translation. Fedorov: "Translation is considered, first of all, as a speech work in its relation to the original and in

connection with the peculiarities of the two languages and with the belonging of the material to one or another genre category". Thanks to literary translation, the phraseological stock of the students' language is enriched. Winged phrases cannot literally fly, but with their figurative flight they make our speech more interesting and dynamic. We did not invent Phraseologisms in the process of dialogue, but we take them from linguistic memory, like ready-made bricks for building a figurative and expressive speech. That is why it is important to read a lot of fiction during your student years in order to replenish vocabulary and phraseological stock. Phraseologisms make our speech figurative and lively, they help convey more meaning and do it emotionally and expressively.

Phraseology plays an incomparable role in reflecting the national spirit expressed in the language of fiction. In translation activities, the translation of phraseological units takes the main place. Therefore, the translator himself must be personally aware of this problem. Scientist-translator A. B. Fedorov considers it expedient to use the following method when translating phraseological units:

1. Accurate translation of phraseological units with full preservation of the meaning of their structure.
2. With a partial change in the meaning or form of the phraseological units of the original.
3. The ability to translate phraseological units by selection phraseological units to the originals of their corresponding analogs in the language translation.

At the direction of the author, in cases where the first and second methods of translating phraseological units are inapplicable, it is considered acceptable to replace them with expressions with a figurative meaning available in the target language. This method takes a huge place in the translation process. Each expression or phrase used with a figurative meaning is considered a valid Phraseologism for the translator. The proverbs, sayings and idioms that are part of the phraseological units, created and improved by the people for centuries, became a rich heritage for the younger generation. Proverbs, being one of the genre of oral folk art with a short form, but deep content, were created on the basis of centuries-old life observations of the people, socio-economic, political and cultural experience. Proverbs, according to their social ideological tasks, become the

exponent of the worldviews of the broad popular masses, and in some cases of a certain social stratum or group. For this reason, the thematic volume of proverbs is very extensive, and it will be impossible to limit this volume within the we the in significant reality of life, and in connection with this, there is not a single area if social life that would not find its vivid reflection in proverbs. For example: In Russian! Bad news fly in wings. Five fingers, but all different measure seven times, cut once. To make mountains out of molehills. In the Uzbek language: Yomon so'zning qanoti bor. Besh qo'l barobar emas. Yetti o'lchab, bir kes. Pashshadan fil yasamoq. Proverbs are a huge treasure of our speech for expressing our thoughts clearly, clearly and figuratively, and their application with art makes the work of the writer, the orator's speech meaningful and attractive, contributes to becoming more impressionable for the figurative expression of their thoughts. Comparative study of proverbs and the process of their translation are of scientific and practical importance. It is also worth mentioning the presence of literal, explanatory or descriptive methods when translating phraseological units. For example: in Russian: The one who laughs well. In the Uzbek language: Oxirgi kulgan, yaxshi kuladi. The study of the corresponding equivalents to words and expressions, the use of expressions equivalent in meaning to those disclosed in the work, expanding the limits of the figurativeness of the translation, contribute to a more expressive reading of it. The transition of phraseological units with full preservation of the meaning of words in their structure, being considered one of the most common methods of translation,

contributes to the entry of new phraseological units into the translation language of the work and the enrichment of the phraseological composition of the same language. This position can be clearly seen in the following examples: For example: in Russian: There is healthy mind in a healthy body. In the Uzbek language: Sog'liq-tuman boylik. Proverbs and sayings, having a short form and deep content, are considered a very important means of expressing a clear, clear and imaginative thought. Let's turn our attention to examples. In Russian: The fish goes out from the head. In the Uzbek language: Baliq boshidan sasiydi. We can clearly trace the identity of the component word that make up this proverb in the compared languages. In Russian: What goes around comes around. In the Uzbek language: Nima eksang shuni o'rasan. It becomes clear to us from the above examples that the full equivalent of this proverb exists in the Russian and Uzbek Languages. Many scholars claim the existense of similar proverbs, sayings and in many languages. Experienced in everyday life, having a

good, complete general meaning, having a short voiced form, considered folk wisdom, proverbs are used to liven up speech and in order to make it attractive, imaginative and more meaningful. The process of translating the phraseological units of the originals using the equivalents contained in the target language is considered one of the most common methods of translation. In this method, despite the fact that the form changes, the expression that is closest in semantics is selected. For example: In Russian: To be afraid of wolves - do not go to the forest. In the Uzbek language: Chumchuqdan qo'rqqan - tariq ekmaydi. As a result of the research carried out, it would be advisable to affirm that phraseological units, being diverse in ideological content, spiritual and moral outcome, have characteristic features in their stylistic function. Due to the similarity of the law of thinking in all nations and the existense of beliefs and representations that are close to each other, even in languages differing in structure, the same or similar proverbs can be created and conversations.

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